

Qualitative Assessment of Blood Cells Morphology and Hematological Parameters of Individuals predisposed to Leukemia Biomarkers in Bayelsa State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The examination of hematological parameters provides the opportunity to clinically investigate the presence of metabolites and other constituents in humans. Previous studies have shown that changes in hematological parameters are often used to determine various statuses of the body. Just like other blood disorders, examination of hematological parameters helps in the diagnosis of leukemia by genetic alteration, environmental factors, or exposure to chemicals that cause uncontrolled cell growth by either increasing the chemical signals that cause growth or interrupting the chemical signals that control growth such as tumor suppressor genes. This study is, therefore, set to assess the morphology of blood cells and hematological parameters of apparently healthy individuals predisposed to biomarkers of acute lymphoblastic leukemia in Bayelsa State. Blood samples of 191 healthy participants were enrolled in this study and SYSMEX XP-300 Hematological Analyzer was used to quantify some hematological parameters such as white blood cells, red blood cells, and platelets, respectively. Statistical findings indicate that platelet concentration was significantly higher in males ($134.43 \pm 78.76 \times 10^9/L$) than in females ($217.15 \pm 125.15 \times 10^9/L$) ($P=0.002$; $T=15.32$). There was a significant difference ($P \leq 0.005$) in the WBC, Hematocrit, and Platelet count in different age groups among participants.

Keywords: White blood cells, morphology, RBCs, platelets, hematological parameters

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Introduction

Hematology refers to the study of the numbers and morphology of the cellular elements of the blood – the red cells (erythrocytes), white cells (leucocytes), and the platelets (thrombocytes) in the diagnosis and monitoring of disease (Majovsky & Netuka, 2018). Blood is a crucial and unique circulatory tissue, made up of cells suspended in a liquid intercellular substance (plasma), and its principal job is to maintain homeostasis (Schwartz, 2023). In order to monitor feed toxicity, it is helpful to use hematological components, which include red blood cells, white blood cells or leucocytes, mean corpuscular volume, mean corpuscular hemoglobin, and mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (Ofori & Hsieh, 2014). Hemoglobin is transported by red blood cells (erythrocytes). Red blood cells are crucial in the movement of oxygen and carbon dioxide throughout the body (Richardson et al., 2020). Accordingly, a lower red blood cell count means a lower amount of oxygen being delivered to the tissues as well as a lower amount of carbon dioxide being exhaled back into the lungs (Mayo, 2023). The primary roles of white blood cells and their differentials are to combat infections, protect the body from invasion by foreign organisms through phagocytosis, and to create or at the very least, transport and disseminate antibodies during an immune response. As a result, animals with low white blood cell counts are at a high risk of disease infection, whereas those with high counts are able to produce antibodies during the process of phagocytosis and have a high level of disease resistance (Werman & Brown, 1986), as well as improve adaptability to local environmental and disease-prevalent conditions (Agozzino et al., 2020). Involved in blood clotting are blood platelets. Low platelet concentration indicates that the blood clotting process will take longer, leading to an excessive loss of blood in the event of an injury. Red blood cell percentage in the blood is measured by packed cell volume (PCV), also known as hematocrit (Hct) or erythrocyte volume fraction (EVF) (Schafer, 2001). The delivery of oxygen and the absorption of nutrients are both facilitated by packed cell volume. A rise in primary and secondary polycythemia is caused by higher Packed Cell Volume, which exhibits improved transport (Habler & Messmer, 1997; Yang & Hinner, 2015).

Research in hematology is useful in the diagnosis of many diseases as well as investigation of the extent of damage to blood (Parker et al., 2014). These studies in

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hematology are of ecological and physiological interest in helping to understand the relationship of blood characteristics to the environment (Tough et al., 2017), and so could be useful to ascertain genetic diseases and environmental factors that could contribute to their emergence (Laursen et al., 2014). Hematological parameters are good indicators of the physiological status of animals and humans (de Gonzalo-Calvo et al., 2020), which are also related to the blood and blood-forming organs (Delwatta et al., 2018). According to Lee et al. (2017), hematological data can be used as a baseline for comparison when examining the physiological, health, and nutritional status of individuals.

Laboratory tests on the blood are vital tools that help detect any deviation from normal in the animal or human body (Cornish et al., 2021). Examining blood for its constituents can provide important information for the diagnosis and prognosis of diseases (Basu & Kulkarni, 2014; Padmore et al., 2020), because blood constituents change in relation to the physiological conditions of health – (McQueen, 2018). These changes are of value in assessing the response of humans to various physiological situations (Crosswell & Lockwood, 2020). Changes in hematological indices may be brought about by dietary, environmental, and hormonal factors in addition to genotype, age, and sex (Biadgo et al., 2016). Low nutritious grassland, pasture, stress, parturition, climatic conditions, among other things, significantly modify the blood values of goats, sheep, and other farm animals (Blank & Friesen, 1980). Also, Sheikh et al. (2022) added that changes in hematological parameters are often used to determine various statuses of the body and to determine stresses due to environmental, nutritional, and/or pathological factors.

Just like other blood disorders, leukemia is a blood cancer caused by genetic alteration, environmental factors, or exposure to chemicals that cause uncontrolled cell growth by either increasing the chemical signals that cause growth (proto-oncogenes) or interrupting the chemical signals that control growth (Parsa, 2012). Bleeding and bruising, weariness, fever, and an increased risk of infection are among the symptoms of leukemia (Shams et al., 2021). Blood testing, molecular diagnostics and bone marrow biopsy are commonly used to make a diagnosis of leukemia (Tanasale et al., 2013). The mixture of genetic and environmental (non-inherited) variables is thought to play a crucial role in leukemia development with risk factors like smoking, ionizing radiation,

certain chemicals (such as benzene), previous chemotherapy, and Down syndrome (Fabbri, 2021; Tiffon, 2018). People with a history of leukemia in their family are also at a higher risk (Maia Rda & Wunsch Filho, 2013; Skibola et al., 2014).

Acute lymphocytic leukemia (ALL), acute myeloid leukemia (AML), chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL), and chronic myeloid leukemia (CML) are the four basic kinds of leukemia with a variety of less frequent types (Puckett & Chan, 2023). Cancers of the hematopoietic and lymphoid tissues, which include leukemia and lymphomas, are tumors that affect the blood, bone marrow, and lymphoid system (Baba AI, 2007). According to research conducted in 2010, the United States spends roughly \$5.4 billion on therapy each year (NIH, 2022). Leukemia claimed the lives of around 281,500 persons worldwide in 2010 (Lin et al., 2021). In the year 2000, around 256,000 children and adults worldwide were diagnosed with leukemia, with 209,000 dying as a result. This accounted for about 3% of the over seven million cancer-related fatalities that year, and 0.35 percent of all deaths (Dong et al., 2020; Sung et al., 2021). The importance of environmental factors in oncogenesis was recognized as a result of studies conducted on Burkitt's lymphoma, an African childhood lymphoma in the 1960s and 1970s (Kurth, 1983; Parsa, 2012). Furthermore, the distinct chromosomal aberrations linked to this illness have contributed to our understanding of the function of molecular processes in cancer etiology (Grade et al., 2015; Rossi et al., 2009; Van Opstal et al., 2018). Therefore, we intend to assess the morphology of blood cells and hematological parameters of apparently healthy individuals predisposed to biomarkers of leukemia.

Method, Study Design and Area

This study utilized random sampling method to select apparently healthy individuals of Bayelsa State origin, Nigeria. Bayelsa State's economy is dominated by the petroleum sector because it is a State in the oil-rich Niger Delta. One hundred and ninety-one (191) subjects between 15 – 60 years were recruited from different parts of the state for this research including Yenagoa, the capital of Bayelsa State. The total study population consist of 96 males (50.3%) and 95 females (49.7%); and they are predominantly of the Ijaw ethnic group. These individuals were selected at random for this study irrespective of age, sex, and status to ascertain which age group is prone to leukemic by virtue of risk factors. Samples were analyzed at Federal Medical Centre, Yenagoa, and Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri all in Bayelsa State. Patients who were

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diagnosed with any ailment aside from leukemia were excluded.

Sample Size Determination

The Cochran's formula for calculating the minimum sample size for cross-sectional studies was used (Charan & Biswas, 2013).

$$n = Z^2(1-P)P/d^2$$

Where n = minimum population;

Size, Z = Standard normal variance = 1.96% at 95% confidence level;

d = absolute standard error = 0.05,

p = prevalence of respondent in the All-in children = 15% = 0.15

Substitute into the formula we have: $n = 1.96^2 (1-0.15) * 0.15 / (0.05)^2$: $n = 200.1996 \approx 200$

Ethical Clearance and Informed Consent

The ethical approvals were obtained from Federal Medical Centre and Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital within the Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Informed consent was solicited from apparently healthy individuals in Yenagoa and ten (10) milliliters of blood samples were collected into ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) and transported at ambient temperature to the laboratory for some hematological parameters in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki 2008.

Analysis of Hematological Parameters

Hematological parameters were assayed with SYSMEX XP-300 Hematological Analyzer at the Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, and Federal Medical Center, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. A 3-part differential cell counter uses Coulter's Principle to find the size and volume of the cell. The sample was lysed and dissolved into an electrolyte solution in a container, which also held a smaller container. The smaller container has 2 pumps running to and fro its solution; one creating a vacuum and the other replacing the lost solution. The smaller container has a small hole (an orifice) near the bottom of the container. Coulter's principle was applied through the use of two electrodes. One electrode (the internal electrode) was within the smaller container

but within the electrolyte/sample solution. As the vacuum draws the sample cells through the orifice, the cell momentarily causes electrical resistance to the current as it passes through the orifice. This resistance was recorded, measured, amplified, and processed which could then be interpreted by the computer into a histogram. The 3-part analyzer was able to differentiate between 3 types of WBCs, neutrophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes (Chhabra, 2018).

The sample ID was inputted by clicking the sample ID menu. After mixing the blood samples, the container was taken to the sample probe until the buzzer sounded two times. The LCD screen displayed "Running" and then the tube was removed. The unit executed automatic analysis and printed out the results. The parameters analyzed were White blood cells, red blood cells, Hemoglobin, Hematocrit, Platelets, Lymphocytes, Neutrophils, and Monocytes-basophils-eosinophils mixed.

Peripheral Blood Smear (PBS)

A blood film was made on the blood samples from the research subjects at the Niger Delta University Teaching Hospital, Okolobiri, and Federal Medical Center, Yenagoa, Bayelsa State. A blood smear is made by placing a drop of blood on one end of a slide and using a spreader slide to disperse the blood over the slide's length. The aim is to get a monolayer, where the cells are spaced far enough apart to be counted and differentiated. The monolayer is found in the "feathered edge" created by the spreader slide as it draws the blood forward – (Gulati, 2013). A thin film was made on a grease-free slide, air-dried and placed on a staining rack. The slide was fixed with methanol and flooded with Leishman stain and left for 2 minutes of the slide. The stain was washed off with distilled water, dried, and examined under an oil immersion objective for characteristic features of the blood cells – (Gulati, 2013).

Statistical Data Analysis

Data were analyzed with Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25 and the results were presented in tables and expressed as Standard deviation and frequencies. The mean difference of the complete blood count among research participants was done using Student T-test statistical analysis.

Results

Figure 1. Frequency Distribution of Apparently Healthy Subjects and Leukemic Patients (Control) by Gender

This study recruited 96 (50.3%) males which were distributed between the ages as follows: 15 years – 25 years were 40 (21.0%), 26 years - 35 years were 34 (17.8%), 36 years – 45 years were 16 (8.4%), and 45 years and above were 6 (3.1%). Also, the study recruited 95 (49.7%) females which were distributed between the ages respectively as follows: 15 years - 25 years were 60 (31.4%), 26 years – 35 years were 23 (12.0%), and 36 years – 45 years were 12 (6.3%) as showing in Table 4.1. below:

Table 1. Frequency Distribution of Apparently Healthy Subjects by Age.

Age	Apparently Healthy		Total
	Male	Female	
15 – 25 Years	40 (21%)	60 (31.4%)	100 (52.4%)
26 – 35 Years	34 (17.8%)	23 (12.0%)	57 (29.8%)
36 – 45 Years	16 (8.4%)	12 (6.3%)	28 (14.7%)
45 And Above	6 (3.1%)	-	6 (3.1%)
Total	96 (50.3%)	95 (49.7%)	191 (100%)

Table 4.2: Descriptive analysis of the various hematological parameters based on gender classification.

Results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation and analyzed using the student T-test with statistical significance calculated at a 95% confidence interval and significant scores (≤ 0.005) are highlighted.

	Male	Female	T-Value	P-Value	Remark
WBC	9.49 \pm 12.82	11.50 \pm 29.63	5.11	0.775	NS
RBC	4.41 \pm 1.57	4.30 \pm 1.09	3.54	0.225	NS
HGB	13.22 \pm 2.27	11.80 \pm 1.75	7.42	0.008	NS
HCT	35.69 \pm 11.68	33.85 \pm 8.15	11.28	0.553	NS
PLT	134.43 \pm 78.76	217.15 \pm 125.15	15.32	0.002	S
LYMPH	3.38 \pm 3.27	3.17 \pm 3.41	5.32	0.886	NS
NEUT	2.02 \pm 0.60	2.72 \pm 1.27	2.17	0.664	NS
MXD	0.74 \pm 0.37	0.74 \pm 0.40	1.16	0.101	NS

KEYS: WBC: White blood cells, RBC: Red blood cells, HGB: Hemoglobin, HCT: Hematocrit, PLT: Platelets, LYMP: Lymphocytes, NEUT: Neutrophils, MXD: Monocytes-basophils-eosinophils mixed. **NS:** NON-SIGNIFICANT, **S:** SIGNIFICANT

Hematological parameters of apparently healthy subjects for male were WBC: 9.49 \pm 12.82 x 10⁹/L, RBC: 4.41 \pm 1.57 x 10¹²/L, HGB: 13.22 \pm 2.27 g/dL, HCT: 35.69 \pm 11.68 %, PLT: 134.43 \pm 78.76 x 10⁹/L, LYMPH: 3.38 \pm 3.27 %, NEUT: 2.02 \pm 0.60 %, and MXD: 0.74 \pm 0.37%. Hematological parameters of apparently healthy subjects for females were WBC: 11.50 \pm 29.63 x 10⁹/L, RBC: 4.30 \pm 1.09 x 10¹²/L, HGB: 11.80 \pm 1.75 g/dL, HCT: 33.85 \pm 8.15 %, PLT: 217.15 \pm 125.15 x 10⁹/L, LYMPH: 3.17 \pm 3.41 %, NEUT: 2.72 \pm 1.27 %, and MXD: 0.74 \pm 0.40 %, in the same order. Results from Table 4.3 above shows the comparison of male and female hematological data. Findings indicate that platelets concentration showed a significant increase from 134.43 \pm 78.76 x 10⁹/L in males to 217.15 \pm 125.15 x 10⁹/L in females (P=0.002; T=15.32). Other parameters showed a generally non-significant change across the gender categories.

Hematological parameters of apparently healthy subjects between the ages of 15 years - 25 years were as follows: WBC: $6.36 \pm 3.88 \times 10^9/L$, RBC: $4.10 \pm 1.51 \times 10^{12}/L$, HGB: 12.50 ± 1.39 g/dL, HCT: 32.62 ± 11.53 %, PLT: $194.17 \pm 133.25 \times 10^9/L$, LYMP: 3.75 ± 4.30 %, NEUT: 2.53 ± 1.18 %, and MXD: 0.82 ± 0.44 %. Participants in the age bracket 26 -35 years had mean hematological parameters of WBC: $5.06 \pm 3.84 \times 10^9/L$, RBC: $4.74 \pm 1.16 \times 10^{12}/L$, HGB: 12.41 ± 2.96 g/dL, HCT: 37.62 ± 7.39 %, PLT: $158.59 \pm 67.24 \times 10^9/L$, LYMP: 2.88 ± 0.92 %, NEUT: 2.05 ± 0.61 %, and MXD: 0.68 ± 0.30 %. Participants among the apparently healthy subjects within the age range of 36 – 45 years had mean hematological parameters count of: WBC: $5.02 \pm 0.99 \times 10^9/L$, RBC: $4.49 \pm 0.53 \times 10^{12}/L$, HGB: 14.02 ± 1.15 g/dL, HCT: 39.30 ± 5.32 %, PLT: $142.52 \pm 66.42 \times 10^9/L$, LYMPH: 2.00 ± 0.52 %, NEUT: 2.52 ± 1.32 % and MXD: 0.50 ± 0.16 %. Within the age range of 46 years and above, were observed as WBC: $4.96 \pm 0.02 \times 10^9/L$, RBC: $4.35 \pm 0.83 \times 10^{12}/L$, HGB: 12.07 ± 1.42 g/dL, HCT: 31.40 ± 6.35 %, PLT: $141.00 \pm 45.55 \times 10^9/L$, LYMPH: 2.22 ± 0.75 %, NEUT: 2.58 ± 0.94 % and MXD: 0.53 ± 0.02 % in the same order. However, among all these categories of hematological parameters, significant changes ($P \leq 0.005$) were observed only in the WBC, Hematocrit, and Platelet count. Details of the result are shown in Table 4.3 below:

Table 4.3: Descriptive analysis of the various hematological parameters based on age classification.

Results are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation and analyzed using the student T-test with statistical significance calculated at a 95% confidence interval and significant scores (≤ 0.005) are highlighted.

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AGE	15 - 25yrs	26 - 35yrs	36 - 45yrs	≥ 46yrs	T- valu e	P- valu e	Remar ks
WBC	6.36±3.88	5.06±3.84	5.02±0.99	4.96±0.02	8.96	0.00	S 1
RBC	4.10±1.51	4.74±1.16	4.49±0.53	4.35±0.83	1.86	0.08	NS 2
HGB	12.50±1.39	12.41±2.96	14.02±1.15	12.07±1.42	17.2	0.77	NS 3 5
HCT	32.62±11.53	37.62±7.39	39.30±5.32	31.40±6.35	15.4	0.00	S 9 2
PLT	194.17±133. 25	158.59±67. 24	142.52±66. 42	141.00±45. 55	9.72	0.00	S 2
LYMP	3.75±4.30	2.88±0.92	2.00±0.52	2.22±0.75	4.78	0.86	NS 2
NEUT	2.53±1.18	2.05±0.61	2.52±1.32	2.58±0.94	11.7	0.55	NS 6 8
MXD	0.82±0.44	0.68±0.30	0.50±0.16	0.53±0.02	10.3	0.33	NS 2 2

KEYS: WBC: White blood cells, RBC: Red blood cells, HGB: Hemoglobin, HCT: Hematocrit, PLT: Platelets, LYMP: Lymphocytes, NEUT: Neutrophils, MXD: Monocytes - basophils-eosinophils mixed,

Plate 1: Representing peripheral blood film of apparently healthy research subjects showing the distribution of normal blood cells.

Plate 2: Representing peripheral blood film of control leukemia diagnosed research subjects showing distribution of blast cells in the film. Arrows above showing blast cells in the film.

Discussion

This study evaluated some hematological parameters and blood morphology as biomarkers in acute lymphoblastic leukemia. A total of 191 persons were enrolled in this study. The evaluation of hematological parameters included White Blood Cells (WBC), Red blood cells (RBC), Hemoglobin (HGB), Hematocrit (HCT), Platelet (PLT), Lymphocytes (LYMPH), Neutrophils (NEUT) and Monocyte-basophils-eosinophils mixed (MXD).

White Blood Cells are the body's defensive mechanisms against infectious disease and outside invaders, showing a statistically significant increase of WBC among apparently healthy subjects between all age brackets amongst all categories in this study. This increase which is referred to as Leukocytosis may be due to leukemia, allergic responses, asthmatic attack; inflammatory conditions, rheumatoid arthritis, inflammatory bowel disease or vasculitis; infections such as bacteria, fungi, or parasites, which may be attributed to weakened immune responses (Bewersdorf & Zeidan, 2020). This has previously been reported that many variables, including age, gender, race, altitude, activity level, pregnancy, and others, have an impact on the hematological parameters. As a result, individuals of all ethnicities, ages, and genders have varying normal hematological reference values (Song & Li, 2020).

Red blood cells (RBCs) also known as red blood corpuscles are the most common form of blood cells in humans and animals. Hemoglobin in RBCs helps in

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transporting oxygen throughout the body (Kuhn et al., 2017). Our study shows that RBC count among different gender and different age brackets was not statistically significant. This study agrees with Sender et al. (2016), showing that about 84% of the cells in the human body are 20–30 trillion red blood cells and nearly half of the blood's volume (40% to 45%) is red blood cells. Hemoglobin levels observed in this study fall within the normal range thereby upholding non-significant status when analyzed with student-test. Previous studies reveal that red blood cell count, packed cell volume (PCV), and hemoglobin concentrations are usually high at birth, decline during childhood, and then gradually rise during puberty until they approach typical adult values (Bogdanova & Kaestner, 2018; Turkson & Ganyo, 2015; Tyrrell et al., 2021). Then, as people age, these values tend to deteriorate, particularly in men. Men have these values in greater abundance than women do after puberty. Leukocyte counts differ by gender between the ages of 21 and 50, with women having higher numbers than men (Kverneland et al., 2016; Santimone et al., 2011).

Hematocrit, which is the volume percentage (vol %) of red blood cells (RBC) in blood was measured as part of some hematological parameters analyzed. Results from this study show the comparison of male and female hematological data. Although hematocrit levels among the male and female gender reveal no significant increase but show a statistically significant increase in the different age categories. This study is in line with previous studies that proposed the possibilities of different variables that may impact hematological parameters like age and others. As a result, individuals of all ethnicities, ages, and genders have varying normal hematological reference values (Fiske, 2017).

Platelets, also called thrombocytes, are components of the blood whose function (along with the coagulation factors) is to react to bleeding from blood vessel injury by clumping, thereby initiating a blood clot (Laki, 1972; Lefrancais et al., 2017). Results from this study show the comparison of male and female hematological data. Findings indicate that platelet concentration showed a significant increase from 134.43 ± 78.76 in males to 217.15 ± 125.15 in females ($P=0.002$; $T=15.32$). Other parameters showed a generally non-significant change across the gender categories.

The mean standard deviation of platelet of the various age for apparently healthy subjects were observed as follows: age 15 – 25 years (194.17 ± 133.25), age 26 – 35 years

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(158.59±67.24), age 36 – 45 years (142.52±66.42), age 46 years and above (141.00±45.55). However, among all other categories, significant changes ($P \leq 0.005$) were observed in platelet count. This significance may be due to aplastic anemia, vitamin deficiency, leukemia, cirrhosis, consumption of too much alcohol, iron deficiency, and exposure to chemotherapy, radiation, or toxic chemicals (Greenburg, 1996).

Lymphocytes are a type of white blood cells in the immune system. The mean standard deviation of lymphocytes for apparently healthy test subjects was observed as follows according to the different age groups: age 15 – 25 years (3.75±4.30), age 26 – 35 years (2.88±0.92), age 36 – 45 years (2.00±0.52), age 46 years and above (2.22±0.75). Analysis of lymphocytes done with student T-test along with all other categories shows no significant changes ($P \leq 0.005$) which means there were within the normal ranges for both genders and of the different age brackets.

This study reveals that the mean standard deviation of neutrophils for apparently healthy subjects was analyzed across different age groups and was found as follows: age 15 – 25 years (2.53±1.18), age 26 – 35 years (2.05±0.61), age 36 – 45 years (2.52±1.32), age 46 years and above (2.58±0.94). Neutrophils as part of the disease-fighting cells, fight infection during the beginning (acute) phase of inflammation, particularly bacterial infection, environmental exposure (Witter et al., 2016), and some cancers (Hedrick & Malanchi, 2022; Malech et al., 2014). On the other hand, the mean standard deviation of Monocytes-basophils-eosinophils mixed for apparently healthy subjects were found to be as follows: age 15 – 25 years (0.82±0.44), age 26 – 35 years (0.68±0.30), age 36 – 45 years (0.53±0.02), age 46 and above remain unchanged.

Plate 1 from this study represents the peripheral blood film of the research subjects showing the distribution of normal blood cells. This is also in line with previous reports, that approximately 84% of the cells in the human body are 20–30 trillion red blood cells and are normally not deformed in the absence of a diseased condition (Sender et al., 2016).

Plate 2 in this study represents the peripheral blood film of control leukemia-diagnosed research subjects showing the distribution of blast cells in the film. Arrows in the blood film showing blast cells predominantly visible in the film. This study agrees with

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Vardiman et al. (2009), as blood film shows abnormal proliferation of blast cells which usually begin in the bone marrow and results in high numbers of abnormal blood cells.

Conclusion

It is possible to evaluate the health and physiological status of the people and animals under consideration using hematological parameters and our knowledge of them. Changes in these variables have been investigated in humans from various tribes, cultures, geographical regions, and ethnic groups as well as in many animals such as cattle, sheep, wily Albino rats, goats, and so on. This study of hematological data of apparently healthy subjects by age, tribes, and ethnicities within Bayelsa State does not reveal statistical significance. Apparently, statistically significant data was observed in gender, indicating that platelets concentration showed a significant increase from 134.43 ± 78.76 in males to 217.15 ± 125.15 in females ($P=0.002$; $T=15.32$) while other parameters within both genders showed a generally insignificant change across the board. On the other hand, hematological data of apparently healthy subjects by age showed significant changes ($P \leq 0.005$) as observed in the white blood cell, hematocrit and platelet count only. These changes may be attributed to allergic responses, inflammatory conditions, and infections such as bacteria, fungi, or parasites because participants show no physiological changes in their health and there was no confirmed ailment as at the time of this study.

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